

What is the Mean of Human in Human Resource Management: A Phenomenological Study for the Manufacturing Organizations of Karachi?

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Abstract:

Humans are considered as a social being with rights and freedom, but for organizations they are the source of input for their production. In this research, it is tried to explain the real meaning of human for organizations, for some Human are most important to them yet through their few practices they have shown that actually they consider them as like other resources. In this research interviews were conducted from 03 of the manufacturing organizations from Karachi, Pakistan. Research paradigm used in this research would be post positivism because it will give a room for AD HOC modification and poppies falsification of their defined/ narrated definition of human (by HRM department of organization) after analysis from personals from HR Department and one who actually experience their practices.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Phenomenological Study

Introduction

Etymologically the word Human is borrowed from Latin word "Humanus" which means "of or belonging to man". Human is one who treat others like he want others to treat him, beside this they even treat all living things as their friend and respect them equally regardless of their nature. Scientifically, humans are termed as Homo-sapiens, whose mental abilities are remarkable as compared to all other living things. Human can create complex and new ideas with the help of their minds and also solve them accordingly. When these social beings work together to achieve one common goal they form organization and if these social beings are not managed properly they will result in conflict between one another. The branch of management science that deals with the management of humans in order to maximize their performance and achieve strategic objectives of the organization is termed as *Human Resource Management*.

01- Problem Statement

Humans are considered as social beings with rights and freedom, but for most of the organizations they are the source of input in production process. The primary purpose of this phenomenological study is to explain the meaning of human in human resource management as perceived by the manufacturing organizations of Karachi, Pakistan.

At this stage of research, Human Resource Management (termed as HRM) means, a department responsible for sourcing, hiring, development, benefits and ensuring the practices in line with standards of the industry as prescribed by LAW.

02- Research Questions

Interviewing the personals from HR departments of manufacturing sector organizations of Karachi and observing the practices, the following question guided the study: What is the mean of human in human resource management? Further, the following sub-questions are used to support the above mentioned question.

1. How do people from HR perceive the meaning of human in HR?
2. What are their practices?
3. Does the meaning vary significantly in narrated definition and practices?

03- Significance of Study

Results of this study will help of define the real meaning of Human in HRM from the position of manufacturing organization of Karachi, Pakistan. The concluded results and the findings made on the basis of research questions will help in fulfilling this purpose. This study will also help the HR and academicians to update the meaning of Human as per practices and in future define it accordingly.

Literature Review

Economic development is considered as one when we uplift someone above from poverty line, and in that economic development innovation is considered as one of most important factor (Smith, 2005). The importance of the above mentioned statement is clearly evident from the fact that in 1987 a Noble Prize was given of Mr. Robert Solow for his technological progress and innovation. As the innovation and technological advancement are becoming more and more important day by day, and especially as a result of globalization which has made this world as a global village, it became very much important for organizations to survive in this competitive environment.

As a matter of fact innovative factors no doubt contribute towards the improvement and development and like all others company's tangible and intangible resources also became a source of competitive advantage (Smith, 2005). On the other hand according to Wernerfelt (1984), competitive advantage came to company as a result of valuable transformation and intangible resources present in the organization. Peteraf (1993), has supported the idea and as per his research through proper transformation one can easily convert the short term competitive advantage into long term advantage. With a proper focus on theory of dynamic capabilities, an organization should keep in consideration that how would it arrange the resources, develop them and finally connect them (Wade & Hulland, 2004). This theory works with a basic assumption that a organization can convert short term competitive advantage in to long term if and only if it use its fundamental resources effectively. One should also keep in consideration the fast changing market environment where reward is given to those who change with market and prove themselves to be better than others. In such a case one might face the problem of productivity loss and might think that technology can overcome that loss, but they are wrong because such loss can only be recovered through human capital. The above mentioned claim is well proven by the fact that the concept of wealth has changed from natural resources and physical resources to human resource, which overall forms the 80% of the wealth of the world.

According to the research of Daglio, Gerson, and Kitchen (2014), among all the factors that can impact positively in an organization, human resource management is of most importance. It includes take care of employees in terms of their competencies, creativity and reward. It is also important because a diverse workforce results in synergy effect.

Human resource is a department responsible for sourcing, hiring, tracking, development of personnel, and keeping in track the practices associated with local and foreign LAW if applicable

Term Human Resource (HR) was first used in 1960, at that time labor relations started to gain more attention especially in the areas of motivation, organizational behavior, and selection process. As per the general concept HR is considered to be responsible for four basic areas, dealing with current employee concerns, hiring new employees, dealing with separation process, and finally morale improvement of employees. But the shape of HRM is changing day by day and that change includes both strategic and comprehensive change through which they manage people and also the workplace. The definition of human as explained verbally by HR department and as shown through practices vary significantly, by their practices these organizations have shown that in actual their human / personnel are their resource for some of them they are valuable resource and for others they are just input in order to get their out. As explained by one of the CEO, "why to invest in human, when they

have a known intention to leave the organization?” reply from HR manager, “And what if they remain in the organization?”

Research Methodology

As per the literature studied for this phenomenological study regarding Human and Human Resource Management along with its importance for the organization. The purpose of this qualitative study is to explain the meaning of Human in Human Resource Management as a lived experience from the perspective of HR personals and workers. This study is focused to identify the variations in meaning as defined by HR Department and exhibited by them through practices.

01- Research Questions:

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02- Epistemology, Methodology and Theoretical Perspective:

This study has adopted phenomenology as a research methodology in which theory of knowledge is constructed and known as constructivism. In this epistemology knowledge is constructed through social process, there is no absolute truth and results are found inductively. In this process generation of meaning through individual perspective is of great importance (Crotty, 1998). Furthermore according to constructivism human beings made meanings in their mind as they engage with the world (Crotty, 1998).

As far as theoretical perspective of this study is concerned it would be interpretive as defined by Merriam (2002), it is a study where the researchers primary focus remains on the object that how his/her participants interpret the situation or phenomenon. According to Rossman and Rallis (2003), it is a paradigm of research in which a researcher make an effort to understand the world from the perspective of an individual's lived experience.

Interviewing is done in order to get the information about the perspective of individual. According to Hesse-Biber (2007), Semi-structured interviews are used when the objectives of the research are specific and debatable. In this study semi structured interviews were used and they were analyzed through the process of coding.

03- Research Design:

- a. **Human Subject Approval** – prior to conduct an approval a consent form was taken from the participants and they given free time to study it and raise any question if they want, further it is also allowed to them to skip any question and leave the interview at any time if they want.
- b. **Participants** – participants selected for this study is selected on the basis on convince sampling while keeping in consideration their experience and relevancy with the topic. They all are invited through phone calls.
- c. **Research Site** – out of six interviews three were conducted within those organizations (one from each) and remaining three were conducted on a mutually selected area.
- d. **Data Collection** – as this study deals with primary data so the tools used for data collection is semi structured interview Sanders (1982), and observation. Semi structured interviews are one in which

questions are formulated on the subject topic but they are asked in a flexible manner depending on the individual to whom we are interviewing (Quinn Patton, 2002).

- e. **Data analysis** – the data analysis was done through a multi-phased approach. 1. Organize the data
2. Theme formation 3. Open coding and 4. Reviewing and analysis

04- Validity of Data:

In qualitative studies, it is very important for a researcher to ensure the validity and soundness of data (Miles & Huberman, 1994). According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), ensuring validity is a process of qualitative research in which the researcher ensures the consistency and accuracy.

- a. **Internal validity** – in order to ensure the internal validity of the qualitative study (Creswell & Creswell, 2017); Merriam (2002), have identified a number of methods, out of those methods in this study we have used the two.
- i. Triangulation – as explained by Merriam (2002), a process to collect data from multiple sources or by use of multiple methods. There are four type of triangulation in this study we have used only one i.e. Data Triangulation.
 - ii. Peer review – it is a process in which your peer review your study and comment accordingly (Merriam, 2002). In this study the researcher have done the peer review from MS Student of Sukkur IBA.

05- Ethical Issues:

It is very important for a researcher to ensure the dynamic process of ethical research (Smith Jonathan, Flowers, & Larkin, 2009). The informed consent document was given to each participant and they were also provided with the opportunity to ask any question, skip any question during interview for which they don't feel comfortable in answering to quit themselves from the participation at any time in study. Further, their names were changed in the research in order to protect their identity.

- a. **Role of Researcher** – as this study depends upon the primary data collected through semi structured interview so, I as a researcher act as a primary instrument (Quinn Patton, 2002). My primary responsibility includes development of strong relationship with the participants based on trust.

06- Limitations:

The following are the limitations faced by the study,

- a. Time Limitation
- b. Resource Limitation
- c. Access limitation

07- Research Philosophy:

This study is qualitative study based on phenomenology and philosophical paradigm used in this study is Post-Positivism, which is also termed as methodological pluralism (Wildemuth, 1993). As per study there are 03 paradigmatic determinants, ontology (study of reality), epistemology (knowledge we have about reality), and methodology (strategy used). According to the perspective of post positivism we cannot get the knowledge in its absolute form (Krauss, 2005). This study aims to compare the meaning of human as described by human resource department with their real practices. If they are in line with the definition this study will simply accept and endorse it or else it will go for Ad Hoc Modification of for Falsification.

From epistemological point of view this study works accordingly with quantum mechanism, according to which we can never know about the absolute truth/ reality which means the exact definition for human in HRM is impossible to define and no matter how good we conduct our study there will always remain a room for

rejection. Apart from this it also means that the definition of human in HR is relative and it change with change in organization, time and context.

As per the philosophical view point of this approach one can never know about all the definitions of human in HRM. In order to have the knowledge about human in HRM we must study its one aspect at one time, which means we must keep all other things constant. In post positivism, epistemologically we are incapable of knowing the reality in its totality. Further, according to post positivism the relationship between the knower and the known is inseparable and during research knower get influenced from the known, as a result there would be more subjectivity.

From ontological point of view it is only possible to predict the meaning of Human in HR until we have a simple system, at the time system will become complex it would become hard for us to predict about the definition of human in HRM.

We can never derive all on the basis of sum but we can always refute all on the basis of sum. Post-positivism mainly relies on induction which is not conclusive and hence provide us a space for rejection. In this study our comparison that how manufacturing organizations of Karachi explain human and how they actually treat them will provide us two options either to reject the narrated definition of human or to go for Ad Hoc Modification in the meaning of human.

08- Post-Positivism:

It is a research approach that can be used in both qualitative and quantitative studies. In this a researcher will start with believe that, scientific thinking and working process is not much different from the one we do in our daily life. There is not a great difference between scientific reasoning and common sense, except the difference of degree. During scientific reasoning one must think that the observations are verifiable, consistent and accurate whereas in our daily life we do not think so carefully, which means our degree of thinking vary in both events.

In post-positivism, one of its simplest forms of philosophy is CRITICAL REALISM. In this one believes that reality is independent and our perception has no effect on it. Furthermore, reality is one about which science can study if there is a thing about which a science cannot study than that is not a reality. This concept fall under the school of thought which is totally in opposite of subjectivism, who believes there is no external reality.

Some researchers believe that positivists are realist and the only difference between them is that for positivist all observations and data is fallible and contain some biases or errors which lead us to the conclusion that every theory of this world is revisable. Further if the theory is not revisable it does not means it's true, it is the best possible explanation until that time when we find some evidence to revise it.

Post-positivism suggest to use multiple methods to collect data and to ensure its soundness it suggests the method of triangulation. According to post-positivism all observations are theory based and all researchers are biased from start, even sometimes they themselves don't know it or if they know they ignore it.

Pot-positivism is in opposite of the idea presented by relativist i.e. incommensurability – believe that two people can never understand each other because they both have different experience and culture. As a result we conclude that post-positivism believes in constructivism, means every individual of the society form their own view based on their perception. And as both observation and perception are fallible, our data collected in post-positivism would be imperfect which ultimately makes us unable to arrive at absolute truth/ reality.

09- Objectivity and Post-Positivism:

According to post-positivism objectivity is an attribute/ characteristic that is present in an individual researcher. It is because that researcher is responsible to put aside all his/her beliefs and biases and see the world with the approach of objectivity, what world “really” is? This school of thought believes that an individual can never achieve absolute objectivity and see the world what it really is. All researches conducted which are theory focused ultimately make us biased about the subject.

In order to achieve objectivity post-positivism suggest the method of triangulation and as per this schools of thought, it is almost impossible to get absolute objectivity but one can always approach towards it.

Data Analysis

01- Participants Profile:

- a. **Qadir** – he has done BBA from Sukkur IBA and works as HR Executive since 2014.
- b. **Faizan** – he has done MBA from MAJU, Karachi and works in Finance Department since 2015
- c. **Akber** – he has done MBA from SZABIST Karachi and works as Talent Acquisition Manager since 2013
- d. **Minhaj** – he has done MBA Marketing from SZABIST Larkana and works as a Sales Manager since 2015
- e. **Owais** – he has done MBA from IoBM and works as HR Manager since 2016
- f. **Sheraz** – he has done BBA from Karachi University and works and Sales Executive since 2015.

02- Analysis:

Through analyzing the interviews by the method mentioned above we have developed common themes like resource, animal, output, and utilization. This has helped us in defined the term human and comparing it with the narrated definition of the HR department. Observations has played a vital role in developing the definition of human with respect to the conditions and context.

Discussion and Conclusion

Once in a decade a call is made that our Human Resource Department is destroying us. Sometimes this call prove to be right because now a day HR is given those responsibilities that even do not fit with its existence, or given the task that they can never achieve alone e.g. changing the organizational culture. Sometimes the role of HR is only to deceive the personnel in order to get short term results and during this they deviate from their narrated definition of human and treat them even worse than animals.

As per the research it is concluded that the definition narrated by the HR department of the manufacturing organizations and their practices vary a lot. One of the reasons for this variation is context in which we have observed and the context in which they have described us the meaning of human. Humanity means taking care of others but in HR if someone is not performing up to the mark and proves as a loss for organization than they have to separate it from organization; in such a situation no one can question their humanity. Similarly if manufacturing organization according to them human is their most important resource it is because without them there would be no output and machines cannot work by themselves they need someone to operate them. But in practice they treat them as like other input material. Their working conditions are worse and shifts are long without proper benefits, facilities and wage. They treat them like animals which ploughs the field.

So, in nut sheet the definition of human in human resource management vary a lot from organization to organization. The updated proposed definition of human in human resource management for manufacturing organizations is, “a type of input that is utilized at its optimal level to achieve maximum output”

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